

SUPPLEMENTARY FILE

1. PRE-TEST FOR IPC-IMPLEMENT TRAINING

Full Name.....

Facility Name.....

Department.....

Cadre.....

Date.....

Instructions

Answer all questions

Select the correct response for each question

Time allocated: 15 minutes

1. Which of the following is a key characteristic of collective leadership in healthcare teams?

- A. Shared responsibility for decision-making and accountability among the team
- B. Individual leaders making decisions in isolation
- C. Hierarchical leadership with clear top-down communication
- D. Limiting collaboration between departments to improve efficiency

2. How does collective leadership in a healthcare setting enhance team performance?

- A. It centralises decision-making to a single leader, streamlining communication.
- B. It prioritizes individual professional development over team goals.
- C. It focuses solely on the roles of healthcare administrators, leaving clinical staff with minimal input.
- D. It fosters collaboration, diverse perspectives, and shared accountability, leading to better patient outcomes.

3. IPC-Implement focuses on the following domains to improve infection prevention and control to reduce healthcare acquired infections

- A. Occupational health, Waste management, Linen management
- B. Medical wards cleaning, Theater scrubbing, General hand hygiene
- C. Hand hygiene, Aseptic techniques, Environmental management
- D. Standard precautions, Wound dressing, Surgical procedures

4. What are the six links in the chain of infection?

- A. Infectious agent, reservoir, portal of exit, means of transmission, portal of entry, susceptible host
- B. Pathogen, immune response, transmission, environment, host, recovery
- C. Bacteria, viruses, fungi, parasites, prions, spores

D. Contact, airborne, ingestion, direct, indirect, excretion

5. What is the estimated burden of HAIs in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs)?

A. 1%–5%

B. 5%–19%

C. 10%–30%

D. 20%–50%

6. What is the best way to prevent Catheter Associated Urinary Tract Infections (CAUTIs)?

A. Avoid urinary catheterization unless necessary

B. Change catheters every 12 hours

C. Use antibiotics with every catheter insertion

D. Flush catheters with antiseptics daily

7. According to WHO, how many core components should an IPC program have?

A. 4

B. 6

C. 8

D. 10

8. In IV cannulation, the appearance of a “flashback” indicates:

A. Incorrect needle placement

B. Entry into the vein

C. That the cannula is blocked

D. That the patient is having an allergic reaction

9. What is the main objective of environmental cleaning in a healthcare facility?

A. To reduce the burden of pathogens on surfaces and in the environment

B. To create a sterile environment free of all microorganisms

C. To increase the workload of cleaning staff

D. To replace the need for hand hygiene

10. How is a surgical site infection (SSI) defined?

A. An infection that occurs at a surgical site preoperatively

B. An infection that occurs at the site of surgery post-operatively

C. Any redness near a surgical incision

D. Only infections that cause fever

11. Standard precautions in healthcare primarily aim to:

- A. Ensure all patients receive the same treatment
- B. Prevent transmission of pathogens using basic infection control measures
- C. Replace the need for isolation
- D. Limit the use of personal protective equipment (PPE)

12. How long is it recommended to use an alcohol-based handrub for effective hand hygiene?

- A. 10–15 seconds
- B. 20–30 seconds
- C. 40–60 seconds
- D. Over 1 minute

13. Under which circumstance should soap and water be used instead of alcohol-based handrub?

- A. When hands are not visibly soiled
- B. Only during surgical procedures
- C. After every patient contact
- D. When hands are visibly dirty or contaminated

For questions 14 and 15, indicate whether the statement is True or False

14. HAIs can be completely eliminated with proper IPC measures

True/ false

15. Environmental cleaning protocols should include regular audits and objective assessments, such as using fluorescent markers

True/false

2. OBSERVATION TOOLS

a. Healthcare Worker Observation Tool: Urinary Catheterization

Observation details	
Study team member initials	
Observation record ID	
Date of observation	
Facility name:	
Healthcare worker being observed? (Circle one)	Clinical officer Nurse Doctor Other

	Fully compliant	Non-compliant	Not applicable
Preparation			
Explains the procedure to the patient			
Screen and prepare bed for procedure: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fold linen to bottom of the bed and leave patient covered with a blanket 			
Prepares necessary sterile equipment and supplies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Sterile urinary catheter</i> <i>Sterile drape</i> <i>Chlorohexidine or povidone-iodine solution</i> <i>sterile syringe filled with sterile water</i> <i>Sterile gloves</i> <i>Examination gloves</i> <i>Sterile gauze or sponge-holding forceps</i> <i>Ky gel (lubricant)</i> <i>Urine bag</i> <i>Adhesive tape</i> 			
Performed hand hygiene			
Positioned the patient in supine or dorsal position			
Placed clean but nonsterile drape towel under the buttocks			
Have an assistant available if possible			
Hand hygiene before catheterization and put on examination gloves			

Hand hygiene is performed correctly <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Hand wash ○ Alcohol based hand rub 			
Pre- insertion tasks			
Opened catheterization package, keeping bottom of pack sterile			
Poured cleaning solution into galipot and open the catheter outer cover, drop it on a sterile receiver			
Antisepsis before insertion			
Cleaned urethral meatus with chlorhexidine gluconate or povidone-iodine			
For female catheterization: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Swab each labia majora with downward movement using five swab technique ● Separate the labia using the thumb and the index finger of non-dominant hand until procedure is completed ● Swab the middle over the urethra last 			
For male catheterization: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Swab the tip of the penis Hold the penis firmly with the non- dominant hand			
Performs hand hygiene and puts on sterile gloves			
Organizes supplies on sterile field			
Expose tip and apply lubricant along sides of the tips of the catheter			
Insertion			
Uses “non-touch” technique			
Gently inserts the catheter			
Connect urine bag to the catheter Inflate ballon is with required amount of sterile water according to size			
Secures the catheter to the thigh with adhesive tape			
Ensures that there is no obstruction or kinks in tubing			
Ensures that the urinary bag is below the level of Bladder			
Checks that the urinary bag is above the floor			
Healthcare waste and instrument management			
Disposes of healthcare waste in a colour -coded/labelled container			
Cleans patient’s environment after procedure following cleaning guidelines			

Clean any reusable containers/trays with soapy water, plain water and disinfect with 0.1% Chlorine for metals (not undergoing autoclaving) and 0.5% chlorine for plastics.			
Removes gloves and disposes in a leak proof container			
Hand hygiene			
Washes hands with soap and water			
Allows hands to dry			
Document all procedures involving the catheter and drainage system in the medical or nursing notes. At the minimum, these should include; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>the date</i> • <i>the type</i> • <i>the size of catheter</i> <i>the volume of water in the balloon</i>			
Health education to guardians and patients on catheter care, maintaining cleanliness and recognizing signs of infection			

b. Healthcare Worker Observation Tool: IV Cannula Insertion

Observation details	
Study team member initials	
Observation record ID	
Date of observation	
Facility name:	
Healthcare worker being observed? (Circle one)	<input type="radio"/> Clinical officer <input type="radio"/> Nurse <input type="radio"/> Doctor <input type="radio"/> Other

	Fully compliant	Non-compliant	Not applicable
Preparation			
Explains the procedure to the patient and gets consent			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepares necessary equipment and supplies 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clean and disinfect the tray to place materials for cannula insertion or wipe with an appropriate 70% alcohol 			
Hand hygiene before insertion			
Hand hygiene is performed correctly using either: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Hand wash Alcohol based hand rub			
Position the patient to allow optimal visualization of the cannula site (downwards), Positions the arm with support			
Pre- insertion tasks are performed properly to prevent infection			
Checks the IV solution (bottle or plastic bag) to be sure it is correct <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Uses “non-touch” technique to open infusion set 			
Inserts infusion set into solution bottle or bag without touching the opening and the spike			
Fills the infusion chamber and tubing			
Determine the gauge of cannula most appropriate for the patient			
Applies tourniquet above and palpates vein			
The provider performs antisepsis before inserting the IV line			

Puts on clean disposable gloves			
Using a fresh cotton swab, cleans the site with antiseptic 70% alcohol in a circular motion starting at the centre			
Allows antiseptic to dry			
Insertion			
Ensure the bevel of the cannula is facing up			
Hold the patients' arm and places thumb below the chosen puncture site to stabilize the vein			
Enter skin below or to the side of the vein. Flashback should enter the cannula			
Increase cannula 5mm further			
Decrease the angle between the cannula and skin. Thread the cannula over the needle into the vein			
Release tourniquet			
Apply pressure above the tip of the cannula and remove stylet			
Connect cannula to giving set without touching any sterile components			
Secures cannula with adhesive tape/ transparent dressing.			
Stabilize arm if required			
Dispose of the PIVC insertion pack waste according to waste management guidelines			
Removes gloves and disposes appropriately			
Hand hygiene is performed correctly <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hand wash Alcohol based hand rub			
Labels (date, time, initial) the IV insertion site (on the plaster), bottle or bag with the type of additives			
Healthcare waste management			
Disposes of healthcare colour coded/labelled waste in the correct container			
IPC practices implemented to reduce the risk of infection related to IV lines			
Labelling (date, time, initial)			
Condition (infiltration, swelling, redness, pus)			
Dressing is dry, clean, and not tight			
The infusion site is changed every 72 hours			

c. Healthcare Worker Observation Tool: Wound Dressing

Observation details	
Study team member initials	
Observation record ID	
Date of observation	
Facility name:	
Healthcare worker being observed? (Circle one)	<p>Clinical officer</p> <p>Nurse</p> <p>Doctor</p> <p>Other</p>

	Fully compliant	Non-compliant	Not applicable
Preparation			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Check the patient's care notes for any changes in the patient's condition, prescribed dressing solution, frequency and treatment <p>Screen the bed and close nearby window for privacy</p>			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prepares necessary supplies to cover the type, size and location of the wound 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gather all resources/supplies required and put them on a clean trolley A sterile dressing/procedure pack Non-sterile gloves to remove old dressing Sterile gloves for wound cleaning Apron Appropriate solution for cleaning the wound Waste bin 			
Introduce yourself and obtain consent			
Position the patient comfortably and make sure the surrounding area of the patient's space is clean and tidy before you start			
Wash your hands with soap and water for 40 to 60 seconds or use alcohol hand rub and dry them			
Wears appropriate PPE (apron and non-sterile gloves)			

Clean the trolley using soap and water, or disinfectant and a cloth			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Place sterile dressing/procedure pack on top of the tray/trolley 			
Protects the area surrounding the patient's wound with a plastic sheet			
Removal of old wound dressing			
Loosen remove old wound dressing and disposes correctly			
Pours sterile normal saline if dressing is adherent			
Complete a wound assessment (visual, smell, amount of blood/discharge/excretions, colour)			
Removes gloves and disposes correctly			
Washes hands			
New wound dressing			
Puts on sterile gloves			
Open sterile pack on top of the trolley			
Opens any other sterile items needed unto the sterile field using non-touch technique			
Pour antiseptic solution into gallipot or kidney dish			
Place sterile towel appropriately around area to be dressed			
Uses two sterile forceps one for dipping the swabs in the solution and another for wound cleaning			
Swab the wound from inside out using swab only one stroke and discard, if infected, start from clean to dirty area <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Repeat until wound is clean 			
Remove any loose dead tissue			
Repeat the process until wound is clean			
Remove any loose dead tissue			
Dry the wound with gauze swab			
Applies sterile dressing, one layer at a time with forceps			
Discard the forceps into kidney dish			
Secures the dressing with strapping			
Healthcare waste and instruments management			
Fold up the dressing/procedure pack and place all contaminated material in a waste bin			
Disposes of healthcare waste in a colour coded/labelled correctly			

Places instruments in soapy water			
Removes gloves and disposes them correctly			
Hand hygiene after wound dressing			
Washes hands with soap and water			
Clean trolley with soap and water or disinfectant solution as before			
Perform hand hygiene			
Report and document any change in the wound on the patient's chart, your wound assessment and the care you have given			
Provide the patient with some dressing management education and answer any questions before you go			
Surgical antibiotic prophylaxis is stopped Postoperatively			
Checks patient file if antibiotic prophylaxis is stopped			

3. Adapted IPCAF tool

Core component 1. IPC programme		
Question	Yes or No	Comments
1. Is there at least one trained IPC link person in the ward in charge of IPC activities?		
2. Does the IPC link person have dedicated time for IPC activities?		
3. Are there dedicated resources specifically for IPC activities?		
Core component 2. IPC guidelines		
Question	Yes or No	Comments
<p>1. Does your ward have locally adapted/developed standard operating procedures (SOPs)/guidelines addressing ALL of the following IPC measures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • hand hygiene • decontamination of medical devices and patient care equipment • environmental cleaning • health care waste management • injection safety • health and care worker protection and safety • aseptic techniques • triage of infectious patients? 		
<p>2. Does your ward have locally adapted/developed specific, detailed SOPs/guidelines addressing ALL of the following IPC measures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • standard and transmission-based precautions⁶ (for example, specific SOPs for the prevention of airborne pathogen transmission); • aseptic technique for invasive procedures, including wound dressing (if applicable); • prevention of specific types of health care-associated infections based on the local context/epidemiology; • occupational health? 		

3. Are the SOPs/guidelines in your ward based on facility or national or international guidelines (if they exist)?		
4. Do you regularly (for example, once per year) monitor the implementation of at least some of the IPC SOPs/guidelines in your ward?		
Core component 3. IPC education and training		
Question	Yes or No	Comments
1. Do all new front-line health and care workers receive education and training on IPC SOPs/guidelines upon employment?		
2. Do all new cleaning staff receive education and training on IPC SOPs/guidelines upon employment?		
3. Do all IPC staff in your ward receive specific IPC training?		
Core component 4. Healthcare associated infection surveillance		
Question	Yes or No	Comments
1. Is health care-associated infection surveillance undertaken in accordance with national or sub-national plans/policy?		
Core component 5. Multimodal strategies for the implementation of IPC interventions		
Question	Yes or No	Comments
1. Do you use multimodal strategies to implement priority IPC interventions (at the very least) to improve ALL of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • standard precautions • transmission-based precautions? 		
Core component 6. Monitoring/audit of IPC practices and feedback		
Question	Yes or No	Comments
1. Does your ward conduct periodic or continuous monitoring of IPC practices and indicators according to ward priorities?		
2. Do you have trained personnel responsible for conducting IPC monitoring?		
3. Is hand hygiene compliance monitored as a process indicator in your ward?		

4. Do you provide timely and regular feedback on IPC monitoring data to key stakeholders, particularly to the hospital management and senior administration in order to lead to appropriate action?		
Core component 7. Workload, staffing and bed occupancy		
Question	Yes or No	Comments
1. Are there systems in place to reduce overcrowding according to existing guidelines/SOPs?		
2. Are staffing levels assessed in your ward to ensure that they are appropriate according to patient workload, using the facility and/or national tools (national norms on patient/staff ratio)?		
3. Is a system in place in your ward to improve staffing levels when they are considered to be too low according to the assessment?		
4. Is a system in place in your ward to establish the standard bed capacity for the ward?		
5. Does the hospital administration enforce a system to manage the use of space when the designed standard bed capacity is exceeded?		
6. Is bed occupancy in the ward kept to one patient per bed?		
7. Is adequate spacing of more than 1 meter between patient beds ensured in your ward?		
Core component 8. Built environment, materials and equipment for IPC at the ward level		
Question	Yes or No	Comments
Water		
1. Is a safe and sufficient quantity of water available for all required IPC measures and specific medical activities, including for drinking, and piped inside the ward at all times?		
Hand hygiene and sanitation facilities		
2. Are functioning hand hygiene stations (that is, with alcohol-based handrub solution, soap, water and clean single-use towels or, if unavailable, clean reusable towels) available at ALL points of care and service areas?		
3. Are functioning hand hygiene stations available within 5 meters of toilets (at least with soap, water and		

clean single-use towels or, if unavailable, clean reusable towels)?		
4. Are there a minimum of one functional, improved sanitation facilities, equipped with menstrual hygiene facilities, available per 20 users in your ward?		
Power supply, ventilation and equipment		
5. Is there a sufficient and reliable energy/power supply available for performing all IPC practices?		
6. Is reliable electricity available to provide lighting to clinical areas for providing continuous and safe care?		
7. Is functioning environmental ventilation (natural or mechanical) available in the ward?		
8. Are there sufficient and appropriate materials available for cleaning and disinfection (for example, various types of disinfectants, detergents, mops, buckets, etc.)?		
Patient placement and personal protective equipment in the ward		
9. Do you have adequate single isolation rooms or at least one room for the cohorting/physical separation of patients with similar pathogens or syndrome if the number of isolation rooms is insufficient (for example, tuberculosis, measles, cholera, Ebola, severe acute respiratory syndrome)?		
10. Is personal protective equipment available in sufficient quantity for appropriate use for performing all IPC practices for all health and care workers?		
Medical waste management and sewage		
11. Do you have sufficient functional waste collection containers for non-infectious (general), infectious and sharps waste in close proximity at all waste generation points?		
12. Is waste treated and disposed of safely via autoclaving, incineration (850° to 1100°C), and/or buried in a lined, protected pit?		
Decontamination and sterilization		
13. Does your health facility have a dedicated decontamination area and/or sterile supply department (either present on- or off-site and operated by a licensed decontamination management service)		

for the decontamination and sterilization of medical devices and other items/equipment?		
14. Do you reliably have sterile and disinfected equipment ready for use?		

4. Checklist for IPC supplies and resources

The following indicators will be checked bi-weekly on Monday for the previous week				
	Sometimes	Always	Never	
Availability of running water				
Availability of sterile gloves				
Availability of examination gloves				
Availability of sterile swabs				
Availability of Chlorohexidine				
Availability of povidone-iodine				
Availability of alcohol-based hand rub				
Availability of hand-washing soap				
Availability of paper towels				
Availability of dressing packs				
Availability of sharp boxes				
Availability of waste bins				
Availability of waste bin liners				
Availability of colour coded waste bins				

5. Focus group discussion guide - Work improvement teams (WITs)

WIT Roles and Responsibilities

I would like to start with understanding a bit about your role and experiences in IPC

- How do you understand your role as a Work Improvement Team (WIT)? (*Probe: How is everyone [healthcare teams, workers, patients, guardians and visitors] informed about IPC interventions?*)
- What is the composition of WIT members and how are their roles and responsibilities structured in the WIT?
- How are, WIT meetings done? (*Probe: on agenda, discussions, documentation*)
- How do you ensure that IPC interventions are implemented? (*probe on; availability of guidelines, training / reminders/health education, Audits, feedback, continuous quality improvement steps?*)?
- How are WITs supported in implementing IPC interventions? (*Probe on; leadership, facility champions, IPC committee*)
- How do you ensure teamwork to implement IPC interventions? (*probe on meetings/ task allocation*)

Hand Hygiene

- How are hand hygiene facilities allocated/ maintained in your wards/theater?
- How do supplies affect hand hygiene practices in your ward/theater and how do you advocate for their availability?
- How are you addressing everyone [patients, staff, healthcare workers] attitudes towards hand hygiene?
- How is training on hand hygiene conducted? (*Probe: content, type [bedside, online, CPD], duration, challenges?*)
- How do you ensure that the moments of hand hygiene are followed by healthcare workers and guardians? (*Probe; audit tools, documentation, feedback, peer accountability*)
- What can you tell us about availability and utilization of guidelines/SOPs/ protocols/ visuals aids on hand hygiene in your ward/theater?
- How are hand hygiene practices promoted in your ward/theater? (*Probe on: What quality improvement projects/initiatives?*)

Aseptic techniques in wound dressing, catheterization, and cannulation.

- How do you advocate for availability sterile supplies (*Probe: cotton, gloves, forceps*)
- What can you tell us about availability and utilization of guidelines/SOPs/ protocols/ visuals aids on aseptic techniques in your ward/theater?
- How are aseptic techniques promoted in your ward/theater? (*Probe on: What quality improvement projects/initiatives are there?*)
- How are patients and guardians involved in aseptic procedures (*Probe on: health education to patient?*)
- How is training conducted on these procedures; Cadres involved, content, frequency, mentorships?

- How is teamwork achieved during these procedures?

Environmental Management

- How are WITs involved in environmental cleaning? (*Probe: training of cleaners, monitoring*)
- How do you ensure cleanliness of the wards? (*Probe; audit tools, documentation, feedback, frequency? days? peer accountability*)
- How is orientation on use of toilets achieved and monitored? How are toilets effectively utilized by patients and guardians?
- What challenges are faced during environmental cleaning in our ward/theater?
- How is waste segregation and disposal promoted? (*Probe: during aseptic procedures, health education to guardians and patients?*)
- What do you think can be done to improve environmental cleanliness in the wards/theater?

Topics to be listed following observation

Observations will inform some of the questions to be posed by the moderator e.g., “we observed (this happening) on the wards, and we were wondering if you could tell us why...”.

6. Semi-Structured Interview Topic Guide: Hospital leadership and Management

Roles and Responsibilities

I would like to start with understanding a bit about your job and your role in IPC

1. What is your position and role in IPC at this ward/ facility?
2. How are IPC interventions implemented in your ward/facility?
3. Which teams/leadership structures are responsible for implementing IPC activities? (Probe: *on WITs IPC Champions*)

Hand Hygiene

I would now like to know more about Hand hygiene practices

4. How are hand hygiene facilities placed/distributed/maintained?
5. How do you ensure functional infrastructure and availability of supplies for hand hygiene? (probe which hand hygiene supplies are available/not available?)
6. How is training on hand hygiene conducted? (Probe: *content, type [bedside, online, CPD], duration?*)
7. How do you ensure that the moments of hand hygiene are followed in the ward/facility? (Probe; *audit tools, documentation, feedback, peer accountability*)
8. What can you tell us about availability and utilization of guidelines/SOPs/ protocols/ visuals aids on hand hygiene in your ward/facility?
9. How are hand hygiene practices promoted in your ward/facility? (Probe on: *What quality improvement projects/initiatives?*)

Aseptic techniques in wound dressing, catheterization, and cannulation.

10. How do you advocate for availability sterile supplies (Probe: *cotton, gloves, forceps*)
11. What can you tell us about availability and utilization of guidelines/SOPs/ protocols/ visuals aids on aseptic techniques in your ward/facility?
12. How are aseptic techniques promoted in your ward/facility? (Probe on: *What quality improvement projects/initiatives are there?*)
13. How is training conducted on these procedures; Cadres involved, content, frequency, mentorships?

Environmental Management

14. How are WITs involved in environmental cleaning? (Probe: *training of cleaners, monitoring*)
15. How do you ensure cleanliness of the wards? (Probe; *audit tools, documentation, feedback, frequency? days? peer accountability*)
16. How is orientation on use of toilets achieved and monitored? How are toilets effectively utilized by patients and guardians?
17. How is waste segregation and disposal promoted? (Probe: *during aseptic procedures, health education to guardians and patients?*)
18. What do you think can be done to improve environmental cleanliness in the wards/facility?